

A NOTE ON THE LIMITS OF SUPERSATURATION AND THE PARTICLE SIZE OF THE SOLUTE

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Miers (*J. Inst. Metals*, 1927, 37, 331) postulates the existence of a definite supersolubility curve on the high concentration side of the normal solubility curve. For concentrations between the solubility curve (AB) and the supersolubility curve (CD), the equilibrium is meta-stable and supersaturation can exist there, as long as the solution is not seeded. On the high concentration side of the curve CD, the region has been termed labile, and solutions in the region G will spontaneously crystallise until the concentration of the solution falls to that demanded by the normal solubility curve AB. This proposal, though attractive, leaves undecided the question of how definite is the region between the supersaturated and the labile regions and the factors affecting the boundary of the meta-stable region. His experiments led him to conclude that spontaneous crystallisation occurred at a definite temperature on cooling a solution but not above this temperature. However, he cites examples of supercooling without crystallisation. Again, the high supersaturation exhibited by substances like sodium thiosulphate, copper sulphate and others as against sodium chloride etc., are to be explained. It is to be noted that his observations are on thermodynamically unstable systems which lie between the two stable states viz. (i) the saturated solution in equilibrium with the extra solute, and (ii) the state after relieving of the supersaturation by spontaneous crystallisation on undercooling. Unless the steps involved in this transfer are definitely known, it is not possible to establish the limits of supersaturation with any degree of certainty (cf. Ostwald, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1897, 22, 306).

Under conditions of stable equilibrium it has been shown by the author (this *Journal*, 1945, 22, 55) that supersolubility is controlled by the size of the particles with which that solution is in contact. Thus

$$r(S - S_n)/S_n = K,$$

where the terms have the usual significance as before. From this it is at once evident that a solution may be supersaturated for particles of a certain size and at the same time unsaturated for particles of smaller dimensions at constant temperature. It becomes therefore obvious that with different particle sizes various solubility curves could be obtained similar to the normal solubility curve *i.e.*, with macro sizes. $r = \infty$ has been shown to have a maximum limiting value of 5.0μ . Thus A'B', A'B'',..... are the solubility curves with different particle sizes $r_1, r_2, \dots$. There is, however, a limit for this series of curves, defined by the equation $S/S_n = e^{k/r}$. This equation has been shown by the author (*ibid.*, 1948, 25, 57) to be valid for all

values of $k/r < 1$. As it approaches unity, the value of r verges on the dimensions of colloidal particles and in that region there is no longer the heterogeneous equilibrium of solid-saturated solution but is entirely guided by other factors. So, the lower limit for the supersaturation region is defined by $k=1$ or when the value of r is on the maximum side of the dimensions of colloidal range. Hence, the supersolubility region is bounded by the values of $r=5.0\mu$ and $r=50\mu\mu$. Thus under conditions of equilibrium of saturation, solutions with definite particle sizes of the solute, the meta-stable region becomes one of supersaturation equilibria with different particle sizes of the solute and the region beyond is one of colloids with entirely different properties not controlled by conditions of thermodynamic equilibria.

Conditions for Spontaneous Crystallisation on Supercooling.—Considering a point L on the normal solubility curve AB, the saturated solution is in equilibrium with the solute particles of radius $r=\infty$. If assuming that in the process of supersolution at L all the particles are equally affected and the change in r goes through $r_1, r_2, r_3, \dots$ where $r_1 > r_2 > r_3 > \dots$, the effect of cooling adiabatically from T_s , the temperature of saturation, leads to important conclusions. The temperature line parallel to the X-axis cuts the supersaturation curves at points $E_1, E_2, E_3, \dots$. The point E_1 on the A'B' line could be reached when $r=r_1$. E_1L_1 is the excess solubility over normal solubility at T_1 .

FIG. 1

To arrive at this state of supersaturation all particles from $r=\infty$ change to r_1 . Thus one can pass from L to E with change to smaller dimensioned

particles, supercooling maintaining supersolubility. But other factors are also operative. There is a tendency for crystallisation working in the opposite direction at each of the points $E_1, E_2, \dots$. This depends on the number of the nuclei present which are smaller than r at its various values. Thus, at E_1 , where the size of the solute particle is r_1 , the nucleus for growth should depend on the number of particles having sizes less than r_1 . The formation of nuclei is a slow process, while their growth is fairly rapid when once formed. This is an ideal condition where all the particles are, to start with, of uniform size; but in practice the starting is not uniform with reference to the size of the particles, and further, according to equation cited above, the larger particles tend to grow and decrease the supersolubility, and the finer particles tend to dissolve and also act as nuclei for growth of crystals. The final result will depend on the chances of smaller particles dissolving or acting as nuclei for the spontaneous shower and growth of crystals. Thus, for substances like sodium thiosulphate, copper sulphate which show high solubility and also temperature coefficient of solubility, high supersolubility will be maintained on cooling, but for substances with low solubility and also those with low temperature coefficient of solubility like sodium chloride and barium chloride, the tendency for the spontaneous growth and crystallisation will be more evident than maintaining supersolubility on cooling.

Blythe, Martin and Tongue (*Nature*, 1923, 111, 842) derive in the case of mechanical subdivision the equation $N = ab^{-br}$ or $dN/dr = -bN$, which shows that the rate of increase of the number of particles present of any given size with the decrease of diameter is proportional to the number (N) of particles of that size. So, if one starts with particles of two sizes r_1 and r_2 , r_2 being smaller than r_1 , the rate of increase of the number of particles of r_1 is proportional to the number of particles of r_1 . Hence, the number of r_1 , if it is less than that of r_2 , no shower of crystals will form or if r_1/r_2 is great, there is a chance for spontaneous crystallisation and growth. If T_s is the temperature of saturation under ordinary conditions and T_c is the temperature of spontaneous crystallisation and growth, $T_c - T_s$ will be small if r_1/r_2 is great and *vice versa*.